

HISTORY OF TRANSLATION DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN

Babamuradova N.F.

PhD Candidate of Uzbek State World Languages University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14237621>

Abstract. *This article presents a comprehensive examination of the evolution of translation studies in Uzbekistan, highlighting the contemporary challenges and prospects for further advancement in this field. It underscores the significant contribution of historical translation heritage, which serves as a connective thread linking the nation's past and future, thereby underpinning the development of scientific and educational practices in translation. Translation is posited as a crucial mechanism for unlocking cultural identity, a process observable through the centuries as eminent scholars from Uzbekistan have significantly influenced the establishment of translation studies as an independent academic discipline.*

The article places particular emphasis on the current status of translator education within higher education institutions in Uzbekistan. Drawing inspiration from its rich traditions while aspiring towards new achievements, Uzbekistan is actively refining its pedagogical methodologies, positioning its translator training system as one of the most vital in the region. Consequently, translation studies in Uzbekistan continues to evolve as a dynamic discipline that harmonizes established traditions with a commitment to innovation. This field possesses substantial potential, paving the way for the emergence of a new generation of professionals equipped not only to translate texts but also to forge new connections that have the capacity to effect transformative change globally.

Keywords: *translation, translation studies, history of development, culture, Bayt al-Hikma, Al-Beruni, Uzbek school of translation, independence, related languages, resolution, international cooperation.*

Introduction: In contemporary society, translation studies have emerged as both a pertinent and essential component of global processes involving mutual understanding and cultural exchange. As the world undergoes rapid transformations, diminishing language barriers enhance the role of translation as a vital conduit between diverse cultures, nations, and peoples. This discipline acts as a catalyst for interaction, facilitating not only the dissemination of knowledge but also the reinforcement of relationships among various civilizations.

This area is of particular importance in Uzbekistan, where the history of translation is not just pages of scientific treatises, but a real fabric linking cultural heritage with modernity. Every year, Uzbekistan is increasingly taking the path of scientific translation, opening up new horizons for international interaction and cultural dialogue. In the context of globalization, when the world is becoming truly close, it is necessary not only to develop and maintain translation traditions, but also to adapt them to modern requirements in a timely manner. This means training professional translators, developing new approaches to teaching and forming cultural ties that can make the world more harmonious and mutually understanding.

Main part. The origins of the history of translation in the East date back to the 9th century, when a famous scientific organization, Bayt al-Hikma (House of Wisdom), was established in Baghdad under Caliph al-Ma'mun al-Rashid. This center became the most important intellectual

platform for the development of science and philosophy in the Arab world. Among the scientists and philosophers working at the Academy were many representatives from Central Asia, which emphasizes the importance of the region for the scientific progress of that time. Within the framework of Bayt al-Hikma, work was actively carried out on translating many works from various languages, such as Greek, Hebrew, Sanskrit, Syriac and Persian, into Arabic. These translations covered a wide range of topics, including philosophy, science, literature and ethics, and played an important role in the dissemination of knowledge and deepening intellectual exchange between cultures. The activities of the Academy not only contributed to the preservation and development of ancient knowledge, but also contributed to the creation of a foundation for the further development of Islamic and world science, exerting a long-term influence on the intellectual tradition.

Furthermore, among the greatest scholars who had a profound influence on the development of translation in Central Asia, the great scholar Al-Beruni (973–1048) stands out in particular. He not only had extensive knowledge in various fields, but also deeply studied languages such as Greek, Sanskrit, and Syriac, actively using them to work with texts and translate. Al-Beruni, along with such outstanding thinkers as Al-Farabi (873–950), Ibn Sina (980–1037), and Mahmud of Kashgar (1028–1101, 1126), played an important role in the development of world scientific traditions and civilization. These scholars are considered to be among the pioneers in the field of translation, and their contribution to world science and culture is of great importance. They contributed to the development of such disciplines as mathematics, astronomy, philosophy, linguistics and natural sciences, while actively translating scientific and philosophical works from Greek, Sanskrit and Persian into Arabic. Their work not only enriched the Arabic scientific tradition, but also ensured an important cultural exchange that contributed to the dissemination of knowledge between different civilizations. The translation tradition into Old Uzbek was then continued by such outstanding figures as Sayfi Sarai (1321–1398), Alisher Navoi (1441–1501), Munis (1778–1829), Ogakhiy (1809–1874) and Iskhokkhon Ibrat (1862–1937). Ogakhiy was engaged in the translation of historical and artistic works from Persian into Uzbek, including an abridged version of Haft Paykar (Seven Beauties) and a complete translation of Gulistan. In his works, he showed a creative approach, translating such works as Yusuf va Zuleikho and Shokh va Gado, preserving their artistic content and style of the original. Since ancient times, Uzbek people, with their rich cultural tradition, were already familiar with outstanding works of oriental literature translated into their native language. These works have become an integral part of the cultural heritage and history of Uzbekistan. Translation is closely related to the development of Uzbek science and culture. Literary heritage was replenished with new themes, plots and images thanks to translation. That is why the study of issues related to the history of translation is important for restoring the development of Uzbek literature and its relationships with the literatures and cultures of other peoples.

Consequently, the process of formation of translation theory in Uzbekistan began to actively develop in the second half of the 20th century. This process was led not by literary scholars or linguists, but by experienced translators who were directly involved in practical translation activities. Among such outstanding individuals who made a significant contribution to the development of translation practice in Uzbekistan, we can note Jumanazar Sharipov, Sanjara Siddiq, Ibrahim Gafurov, Mikhail Salye and Amonzhan Muminov, Nosir Kambarov and others. Their work had a key influence on the formation of the translation tradition in the country.

In the period from the 1940s to the 1990s, a group of professional translators and translation theorists emerged in Uzbekistan, whose work had a profound impact on the development of this discipline. Gaibulla Salomov (1932–2000) played a key role in the formation and development of Uzbek translation school. His scientific leadership of the translation school contributed to strengthening the theoretical and practical foundations of translation in the country, as well as the formation of a whole generation of specialists in this field. Even at the FIT (International Federation of Translators) symposia under the auspices of UNESCO, warm words were spoken about Uzbek school of translation and translation studies. “A translation school has emerged in Uzbekistan that can compete with the centers of translation studies in the former Soviet Union and abroad”. In addition, scholars of Uzbek translation school have conducted extensive research into both universal and specific aspects of translation theory, with a special emphasis on improving the quality of translation. In their works, they carefully analyzed and examined translations from Russian into Uzbek and vice versa, as well as translations from related languages such as Kyrgyz, Kazakh, Tatar, Turkmen, Azerbaijani and Karakalpak and other languages such as Persian, Tajik, Arabic, Hindi and Chinese into Uzbek. The main attention was focused on such important aspects as the accuracy of conveying meaning and achieving the highest possible quality of translation. Particularly noteworthy is the fact that since the 1990s, after Uzbekistan gained independence, the practice of direct translation from foreign languages, especially from English, has been actively developing, which has become a significant stage in the evolution of translation activities in the country. Independence opened up broad prospects for the development of translation and all types of artistic creativity. This gave Uzbek translators and authors the opportunity to enter the international stage, which contributed to the promotion of our culture and literature to the world level.

Specifically, Professor G. Salomov was one of the first to prove that translation is a phenomenon that includes both linguistic and artistic aspects. The basis of this process is style, which has a broad meaning and covers not only linguistic phenomena, but also creativity, art, and emotional and intellectual creativity. Within the framework of translation, national traditions, historical context, cultural development and reader's perception are taken into account, which gives the process depth and ambiguity. Translation studies has thus become a multifaceted and extensive field of study, covering not only the study of texts, but also a wider range of issues related to the cultural and historical aspects of translation. This approach has led to the formation of a scientific school that studies such elements as national literature, customs and cultural development. Translation studies has become not just a process of transferring meanings between languages, but also a way to demonstrate the richness and possibilities of Uzbek language, as well as a means of recreating world literature in the context of national culture. Thus, translation has become an important tool for enriching literature and exchanging spiritual values between peoples, while the translator is perceived as a creative person who contributes to the development of literature. Uzbek school of translation and translation studies, formed under the leadership of Professor G. Salomov, has gained international recognition, and the scientist himself has become a well-known figure in the world scientific community. His scientific works have found a response in such countries as Slovakia, France, Bulgaria, Turkey and Yugoslavia. Professor Salomov maintained fruitful scientific ties with leading specialists, among whom were L.S. Barkhudarov, S.N. Ivanov, M. Levin (St. Petersburg), M.I. Osmanov (Moscow), G. Aliyev and T. Toirbekov (Baku), with whom he regularly exchanged experiences and research results. In the 1980s, the scientist visited

Czechoslovakia, Bulgaria, the former Yugoslavia and Ukraine, where he gave lectures and presented his scientific achievements. G. Salomov wrote and published in several languages, including Russian, Tajik and Azerbaijani, which testifies to his high linguistic competence. He was fluent not only in Russian, but also in Persian, German, Tajik and other Turkic languages, which confirms his deep knowledge of various cultures and languages, as well as his passion for world traditions and linguistic diversity. In the field of scientific research in the field of translation studies, significant contributions to the development of Uzbek translation science were made by such scholars as Sh. Safarov (2019), Sh. Sirojiddinov (2011), I. Gafurov, A. Muminov, N. Kambarov (2012), G. Rakhimov (2016), I. Tukhtasinov, U. Yuldashev and J. Abduganiyeva. These researchers not only conducted in-depth theoretical research in the field of translation, but also proposed effective methods for solving topical issues related to translation techniques, methods and strategies. Their works pay special attention to the issues of accuracy of information transfer, preservation of stylistic features of the text during translation and ensuring the adequacy of translation from Uzbek into other languages and vice versa.

Thus, their scientific works played an important role not only in the theory of translation, but also in the practical application of translation methods that contribute to the improvement of intercultural communication. The research of these scientists offers new approaches to solving the problems of translating cultural and linguistic features, which allows achieving a high level of accuracy and expressiveness in conveying meanings. Another important aspect is the attention to the issue of mutual influence of literature and culture of different countries through translation, which contributes to a better understanding and transmission of world cultural values. Their works laid the foundation for the development of new academic standards in the field of translation studies and played an important role in improving translation practice, providing a reliable theoretical basis for improving the quality of translations and improving the methodology of translation. In contemporary society, one of the most important tasks in the field of Uzbek translation theory is to determine the key skills that translators should have, as well as to develop effective teaching methods aimed at developing these skills. This requires a comprehensive approach that would take into account both the theoretical and practical aspects of translation. Therefore, it is extremely important to develop educational standards that will allow translators to work at the highest level and meet the requirements for translation quality in the context of globalization.

Additionally, these curricula need to incorporate relevant methodologies that reflect the trends and challenges of modern translation practice, including the use of technologies and specialized translation tools. Such educational approaches will not only help improve the quality of translation, but also significantly increase the competitiveness of Uzbek translation in the international arena, which in turn will contribute to strengthening cultural and scientific ties between Uzbekistan and other countries. The Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, showing foresight and a strategic approach, is implementing a number of important measures aimed at developing and strengthening the role of foreign languages in the country. In this context, the adoption of the Presidential Resolution of May 19, 2021, entitled “On measures to raise the activities to popularize the study of foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a qualitatively new level” has become a key step towards significant progress in language education. This document not only raises the process of learning foreign languages to a qualitatively new level, but also emphasizes the importance of certification of knowledge required of applicants

when entering higher educational institutions. This decree places emphasis on detailed regulation of certification of knowledge of foreign languages for students, which, of course, contributes to increasing the competitiveness of young people and providing highly qualified specialists for the domestic economy.

Notably, in parallel with this important step, the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of May 18, 2018, concerning the improvement of the translation system, became the foundation for the creation of a targeted and systematic strategy for the translation of both world literary works into Uzbek language and works of domestic literature into the international arena. This resolution is not just a document regulating the procedure for translation, but also a kind of bridge between cultures that ensures deeper mutual understanding and strengthens cultural ties at the international level. Leading world works, now thanks to the efforts of the state, are acquiring new sounds in Uzbek language, thereby not only enriching our literature, but also raising it to the international arena. To this end, these steps demonstrate Uzbekistan's readiness to integrate into the world cultural and educational process, giving new life to many valuable works and ideas. It is important to note that such actions, supported at the state level, not only contribute to strengthening cultural and educational ties between peoples, but also play a significant role in the globalization of knowledge and ideas, promoting the growth of the level of intellectual exchange and mutual understanding.

Conclusion. To summarize, it is safe to say that the study of the history and current state of translation in Uzbekistan is like a journey through a rich and multi-layered heritage that is deeply woven into the fabric of world culture. From the first steps of the great thinkers of Central Asia, whose works have been translated and preserved thanks to translators, to modern efforts to promote Uzbek literature in the international arena, translation has always served as a link that connects peoples, eras and cultures. Consequently, translation is not just the transmission of words from one language to another, it is a kind of magic that opens new horizons, builds bridges between different worlds. It is the key that opens the door, allowing you to understand, feel and see the alien in a new light, without losing your unique identity. In this context, translation serves not only as a tool for disseminating knowledge, but also as an important mechanism for preserving and transmitting cultural traditions. It provides an opportunity to hear and understand another voice, another point of view, expanding the horizons of understanding the world. In contrast, looking at the path taken by Uzbek scientists and translators, it is impossible not to note the importance of their contribution to the development of the world cultural and scientific space. Translation has served and continues to serve as a link between different languages, peoples and eras. It becomes a kind of cultural ambassador that promotes mutual understanding and exchange of values, being a catalyst for civilizational progress.

To illustrate modern translation studies in Uzbekistan are a step forward in understanding the global challenges that the world faces in the era of globalization. Translation is becoming not only a science, but also an art that requires skill and sensitivity from performers, the ability to convey not only the meaning, but also the soul of the text. It is important that translation is not limited to scientific or literary texts, it covers all areas of life, from political discussions to personal stories, enriching our perception of the world and each other.

Thus, translation studies in Uzbekistan are not just a scientific discipline, it is the foundation on which the further development of cultural and educational ties both within the country and in the international arena is built. This is a process that inspires the search for new

meanings and values, awakening the desire to exchange knowledge and ideas. As a result, translation remains an integral part of intellectual and cultural progress, which allows the country not only to preserve its uniqueness, but also to actively participate in the global cultural and scientific dialogue. All this emphasizes the importance of translation as an integral part of cultural identity and international cooperation. After all, through translation we gain the key to understanding the world and, in turn, open the world to others.

REFERENCES

1. Kambarov N.M. On the issue of the specifics of teaching consecutive translation. // *Khorizhiy tilshunoslik va adabiyotshunoslik kiyosiy-tipologik tahlili*. - Karshi, 2018.
2. Kambarov N.M. The transformation of linguistic and cultural knowledge and cognitive skills (monograph) // Tashkent, 2019.
3. Musayev K. Interpretation of linguistic and cultural knowledge.–T., 2005
4. Muminov O. Interpreter training exercises // *Content-based Learning in Uzbekistan: Opportunities and Challenges: International Conference Proceedings*. – Tashkent, May 2, 2015. – P.163-165;
5. Tukhtasinov I.M. Interpreter training exercises // *Content-based Learning in Uzbekistan: Opportunities and Challenges: International Conference Proceedings*. – T.: 2018. – 69 p.
6. Translation Quality Assessment Fmq Matenova, Dr Abduganiyeva - *Scientific Progress*, 2023
7. Ilhomzhon Tükhtasinov, Ulugbek Yıldoshev - badiy tarzhimani ykitishning linguistics methods asoslari - “Samarkand davlat chet tillar institute” nashriyoti Samarkand, 2023 (Monography)
8. Tukhtasinov I.M. Tarzhimon tayorlashda kasbiy kompetentsiyalarni equivalentik hodisasi asosida rivojlantirish. *Pedagogy fanlari doktor darajasi uchun yozilgan dissertation*. – Toshkent: 2018. – 229 b
9. Salomov G. Til va tarjima. – T.: 1966. – 103 p. // *History of Translation (Europe and Central Asia)*. – T.: Uqituvchi, 1978. – 152 p.
10. Muminov O. *History of Translation (Europe and Central Asia)*. – T.: Mekhridaryo, 2008. – 128 p.
11. Salye A. - translations of the “Canon of Medicine” by Ibn Sina (Avicenna), “Babur-name” - notes of the founder of the Mughal Empire Babur and “Monuments of Past Generations” by Beruni.
12. Sh. Safarov - *Theory of Compensation of the Past Generations* – 2019
13. Rahimov G. - *Theory of Compensation of the Past Generations* - 2019. – T.: Ozbekiston milliy encyclopedias davlat ilmiy nashriyoti, 2016. – 176 b
14. Sirozhiddinov Sh, Odilova G. *Badiy tarzhima asoslari*. Monograph. – T.: Mumtoz soz, 2011.
15. Gafurov I, Muminov O, Kambarov N. *Tarjima Nazariyasi*. – Tafakkur-Buston, 2012.
16. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated 19.05.2021 No. PP-5117 “On measures to raise the activities to popularize the study of foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a qualitatively new level”
17. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated 18.05.2018 No. 376 “On measures to improve the system of publishing and translating the best examples of world literature into the Uzbek language, and masterpieces of Uzbek literature into foreign languages”